

CERTIFICATION OF ENROLLMENT

Study title: EUS-GUIDED BILIARY DRAINAGE WITH EC-LAMS VS ERCP AS PRIMARY INTERVENTION FOR ENDOSCOPIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DISTAL MALIGNANT BILIARY OBSTRUCTION

IRRB number: IRRB/43/19

(hereinafter referred to as "Study")

Promoter: Humanitas Research Hospital, Rozzano (MI)

(hereinafter referred to as "Promoter")

The Promoter of the Study here certifies that the Centre IRCCS ISMETT enrolled prospectively N° 21 patients in 2023.

Date 14/03/2024

Name: ALESSANDRO FULAZZA

Signature on behalf of the Promoter

Position/Title: MD